

MERGE

MEASURING WHAT MATTERS

Policy pathways to sustainable and
inclusive wellbeing

Deliverable 5.3

Technical and data deep dives: Overview of the workshops

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Contents

Executive summary	7
I. Introduction.....	9
II. The deep dives: Overview of the workshops	11
i. Roundtable on data collection and harmonisation of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing indicators in the EU	11
1. Background and concept.....	12
2. Workshop overview.....	13
3. Key discussions and takeaways.....	13
4. Connection to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages	16
5. Operational guidelines for NSIs (next steps).....	16
ii. Workshop on comprehensive welfare measures	20
1. Background and concept.....	20
2. Workshop overview.....	21
3. Key discussions and takeaways.....	21
4. Connections to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages	24
5. Operational Guidelines for NSIs (next steps)	24
iii. Workshop on new methods in time use surveys.....	25
1. Background and concept.....	25
2. Workshop overview.....	26
3. Key discussions and takeaways.....	26
4. Connection to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages	30
5. Operational guidelines for NSIs (next steps).....	30
iv. Workshops on wealth accounting.....	31
1. Background and concept.....	31
2. Workshop overview.....	32
3. Key discussions and takeaways.....	32

4. Connection to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages	34
5. Operational guidelines for NSIs (next steps).....	34
III. Final reflections and next steps.....	35
References	39
Annex	40

Acronyms used in the report

ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GNP	Gross National Product
HLEG	United Nations High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP
JRC	European Commission Joint Research Centre
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
NSI	National Statistical Institute
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ONS	United Kingdom Office for National Statistics
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIW	Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing
SNA	System of National Accounts
UGent	Ghent University
UN	United Nations

Executive summary

Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW) provides an overarching policy goal to guide governance and policy choices in accordance with European values and for the benefit of its long-term prosperity and resilience. In turn, pursuing this goal requires having the right navigation tools. Yet, despite the emergence of numerous alternative metrics that offer a more holistic view of sustainability, inclusion, and wellbeing compared to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), their uptake remains fragmented and limited. The rapid growth of alternative frameworks, indicators, and metrics has highlighted the need for greater harmonisation in terminology and methodology. Without common standards, communicating results, informing policy, and comparing countries remains challenging.

Another obstacle is the high degree of multidimensionality of SIW. The concept of wellbeing itself consists of many components, and including the layers of inclusiveness and sustainability brings in additional levels of complexity. This makes the creation of headline measures difficult and leads to the frequent use of dashboards instead. However, surveys suggest that multidimensional measurement frameworks can be difficult to interpret and would benefit from stronger institutional support to enhance their policy relevance.

In this scenario, MERGE—a Horizon Europe funded project that brings together research and policy partners to find pathways towards SIW—has conducted a series of **technical and data deep dives (WP5)** aiming to explore selected challenges that limit the application of beyond GDP and SIW indicators. This report offers an overview of the six co-creative workshops that took place in the context of WP5: one focused on data harmonisation and collection for wellbeing and sustainability indicators in the European Union (EU); one on comprehensive welfare measures; two workshops on time use surveys; and two workshops on wealth accounting. While the workshops covered diverse topics, and as such offered specific insights that cannot be simply extrapolated to other areas, it is still possible to identify some cross-cutting discussions that emerged as common threads across these deep dives and that can provide insights into the existing challenges and gaps related to incorporating SIW indicators and beyond GDP metrics into National Statistical Institutes (NSIs) work more holistically. Before diving into these overarching themes, it is worth noting that they combine insights of different nature: While some relate to technical constraints within NSIs, others concern the broader political and institutional contexts in which NSIs operate. Although oftentimes these challenges are interconnected and reinforce each other, it is worth making the conceptual distinction.

Against this backdrop, a first group of reflections focused on the interactions needed to set in motion the technical reforms and statistical innovations necessary for developing SIW measurement frameworks. Partnership between NSIs with academic partners emerged as an important collaboration for exploring cutting-edge ideas and fostering creativity in each thematic domain. Similarly, engagement with “frontrunner” NSIs also plays a key role, offering practical pathways towards implementation. However, to move towards the institutionalisation of SIW metrics, political will and momentum, including coming from international spaces, were recognised as essential drivers at the early stages and beyond.

A second cluster of common reflections was about how to move from ideas to solutions that can be plausibly implemented by NSIs. In this sense, it is worth highlighting that the System of National Accounts (SNA) plays a crucial role in shaping the work of NSIs; thus, when proposals are directly connected to the SNA, they become easier to operationalise. In this scenario, having the SNA more regularly updated would create a fertile ground and space for further innovations. However, it was also noted that feasibility, while important, should not limit ambition.

Lastly, and unsurprisingly, the need for harmonisation also emerged as a common thread. While innovation and creative solutions are developed continuously, efforts are frequently scattered and need to be aligned. Once again, international guidance can help pave the way forward, offering solutions that can be adopted and replicated at the national level. Nonetheless, this should not inhibit national innovation, and NSIs should remain pragmatic in their approach. More widely, it was also highlighted that harmonisation (and innovation) requires proper resourcing, including sufficient funding and appropriate capabilities. At the moment, these issues remain among the most important challenges that NSIs face when it comes to developing and implementing innovative indicators in the area of SIW; a challenge that cannot be solved completely in the technical realm, as it requires policy direction and support.

These overarching insights will also be carried forward into the forthcoming MERGE technical guidelines (D7.1), where they will inform both the analytical framework and the practical implementation guidance. In particular, the chapters on data sources and data collection methods build on the knowledge generated by this report, with a strong focus on harmonising data sources and integrating innovative forms of data. Special attention is given to time use statistics, reflecting their growing importance within the SIW framework and their potential to enhance the measurement of wellbeing, inclusion, and sustainability.

I. Introduction

Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW) provides an overarching policy goal to guide governance and policy choices in accordance with European values and for the benefit of its long-term prosperity and resilience. In turn, pursuing this goal requires having the right navigation tools. Yet, despite the emergence of numerous alternative metrics that offer a more holistic view of sustainability, inclusion, and wellbeing compared to Gross Domestic Product (GDP)¹, their uptake remains fragmented and limited. The rapid growth of alternative frameworks, indicators, and metrics has highlighted the need for greater harmonisation in terminology and methodology.² Without common standards, communicating results, informing policy, and comparing countries remains challenging.

Another obstacle is the high degree of multidimensionality of SIW (see Box 1). The concept of wellbeing itself consists of many components, and adding the layers of inclusiveness and sustainability bring in additional levels of complexity. This makes the creation of headline measures difficult and leads to the frequent use of dashboards instead. However, surveys

Box 1: The SIW framework and its dimensions

The SIW framework is composed of three interconnected dimensions:

- **Wellbeing now:** Ensuring a good life for all today. Includes key determinants of wellbeing, such as health, education, air quality, employment, social relationships, income, housing, security, environmental health, and peace.
- **Wellbeing for all:** Limiting inequalities across social groups. Gauges the distribution of wellbeing determinants and opportunities across spatial scales and social groups, such as gender inequality, income/wealth inequality, risk of poverty, child poverty and discrimination.
- **Wellbeing in the future:** Preserving conditions for future generations. Encompasses biophysical and social conditions for future wellbeing, including climate, biodiversity and other planetary boundaries, demographics and innovation capacity.

¹ See for instance Constanza et al (2024). A Synthesis of Models, Metrics, and Policies for a Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing Future. Available at: <https://mergeproject.eu/synthesis/>

² See for instance Abdallah et al (2025). Data harmonisation and collection for wellbeing and sustainability indicators. Available at: <https://mergeproject.eu/data-harmonisation-and-collection-for-wellbeing-and-sustainability-indicators/>; also referred to as Deliverable 5.1.

suggest that multidimensional measurement frameworks can be difficult to interpret and would benefit from stronger institutional support to enhance their policy relevance.

In this scenario, MERGE—a Horizon Europe funded project that brings together research and policy partners to find pathways towards SIW—has conducted a series of **technical and data deep dives (WP5)**³ aiming to explore selected challenges that limit the application of beyond GDP and SIW indicators. This report offers an overview of the co-creative workshops that took place in the context of WP5 (section II) and a reflection of the common themes that emerged across them (section III). Co-creation is a collaborative approach in which different stakeholders work together to develop ideas or solutions around a specific issue or topic. Rather than acting as passive contributors, all participants are engaged actively in the process through co-creation methods, bringing their own experiences, skills, and knowledge. This shared ownership often leads to more innovative, inclusive, and people-centred outcomes.

As part of their work on WP5, the MERGE consortium hosted a total of six co-creative workshops: one focused on data harmonisation and collection for wellbeing and sustainability indicators in the European Union (EU; section II.i); one on comprehensive welfare measures (section II.ii); two workshops on time use surveys (section II.iii); and two workshops on wealth accounting (section II.iv).⁴ These topics were selected for their relevance: for instance, time use surveys and wealth accounting were identified as priority areas by the UN Network of Economic Statisticians in a series of workshops on Beyond GDP that took place between 2022 and 2023. Through these summaries, readers can learn not only about the concrete activities that took place, but also the highlights from the discussions and the suggested next steps on how to operationalise learnings at the technical level.

³ WP5 is structured around a series of tasks that covered different yet interconnected topics. First, at a higher level, the WP had a task dedicated to the harmonisation and collection of data for wellbeing and sustainability indicators (T5.3). In this task, the focus was addressing data gaps and lack of harmonisation and coordination across Member States. Secondly, the WP included three tasks that focused on specific topics: comprehensive welfare measures (T5.1), time use surveys (T5.2), and wealth accounting (T5.4). Lastly, WP5 also included a task dedicated to modelling different policies using alternative indicators within an ecological macroeconomic model (T5.5). With the only exception of the latter, all the other tasks under WP5 involved co-creative activities, either online or in-person, allowing a wide range of experts beyond our project consortium to feed into the discussions.

⁴ As noted in the previous footnote, WP5 also includes a task focused on modelling different policies using alternative indicators within and ecological macroeconomic models. Since this task did not include any co-creative events, it is not featured in this deliverable. Nonetheless, results from this work will be available in a forthcoming policy brief of MERGE project (D5.2).

While these deep dives did not intend to provide a comprehensive understanding of the SIW field as a whole, the careful exploration of these different areas offers interesting insights which relevance goes beyond each specific case study and can provide a fertile ground for future explorations.

II. The deep dives: Overview of the workshops

In the following pages, we present an overview of the six workshops that took place in the context of WP5 (technical and data deep dives). First, we introduce the roundtable on data collection and harmonisation of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing indicators (Sub-section II.i), followed by the workshop on comprehensive welfare measures (Sub-section II.ii). Sub-section II.iii focuses on the two discussions related to time use surveys; whereas sub-section II.iv summarises two workshops focused on wealth accounting.

These short accounts follow a similar structure, presenting background and concept, an overview of the workshop agenda, objective and participants, a summary of the key discussions and takeaways, the connection with other technical guidelines, and some ideas concerning next steps, focused on operational guidance for national statistical institutes (NSIs).

i. Roundtable on data collection and harmonisation of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing indicators in the EU

This activity took place in the context of Task 5.3 Data harmonisation and collection for wellbeing and sustainability indicators and was led by ZOE Institute, in collaboration with Hot or Cool Institute.⁵

⁵ The final results from this task (including the interviews and the roundtable) are already presented in full detail in a separate deliverable: Abdallah, S., Chevallier, R., Meo, B. & Brosio, M. (2025). *Data harmonisation and collection for wellbeing and sustainability indicators*. MERGE Deliverable 5.1. Available at: <https://mergeproject.eu/data-harmonisation-and-collection-for-wellbeing-and-sustainability-indicators/>

1. Background and concept

Following the United Nations (UN) Pact for the Future, an independent high-level expert group (HLEG) was established to develop a set of indicators that could complement and go beyond GDP. These expert conclusions will be followed by an intergovernmental process potentially paving the way for the adoption of an international 'Beyond GDP' framework across UN Member States.⁶ While they are not all explicitly identified as Beyond-GDP, as of 2024, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) estimates that two-thirds of OECD countries have developed national frameworks, development plans or surveys with a focus on wellbeing (OECD WISE, 2024). In this task, they were referred to as 'Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW)' frameworks. 'While 'Beyond GDP' remains the most widely recognised label for this agenda, there is growing consensus around the term SIW⁷, which more clearly defines the ultimate objective of these measurement efforts: assessing whether societies are delivering wellbeing in an inclusive and environmentally sustainable way. More precisely, this task defined SIW frameworks as *cohesive measurement frameworks incorporating data from multiple sources to assess sustainability, inclusivity and wellbeing so as to provide an accessible one-stop overview of a given society's ability to deliver wellbeing for all - now and in the future*. The work of NSIs and their statisticians is key to operationalising the SIW frameworks and to the success of this agenda at the national level. This task puts the focus on the development and implementation of those frameworks, and notably on the experience of the NSIs. It aimed to uncover perspectives and lessons learned in addressing key issues of data and framework harmonisation that will be crucial for the future of the recommendations of the HLEG.

The team interviewed 19 staff members working in NSIs, government bodies or inter-governmental organisations in 10 countries, covering a wide range of experiences with frameworks for measuring wellbeing and sustainable development. The countries covered include Austria, Croatia, Finland, France, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, New Zealand and Poland. The interviews not only shed light on key challenges but also on promising developments and potential ways forward. The insights from the interviews were gathered in a discussion paper that was presented during an online roundtable workshop

⁶ For more information about the UN HLEG on Beyond GDP and MERGE consortium engagement with this project, see MERGE deliverable 6.1 (Danilaviciute et al. (2026). Summary on EU and UN policy engagement. MERGE project deliverable D6.1. Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.20851296).

⁷ See for instance Rum, I., Hoekstra, R., Jansen, A., Eastoe, J., Kubiszewski, I., Constanza, R., Kaufmann, R., & Biggeri, M. (2024). Are Beyond-GDP metrics converging? Consolidation of the measurement of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing. MERGE, Horizon Europe project. Available at: <https://mergeproject.eu/publications-consolidation-metrics/>

which brought together NSI staff, MERGE consortium members, academics and other technical experts. From the workshop's conclusions, we then reviewed the discussion paper to finalise the final report (Abdallah et al., 2025, available in the Annex).

2. Workshop overview

The roundtable took place online on 20th November 2025. It brought together 18 participants, including seven people who had been interviewed in the previous phase of work, two additional experts working in NSIs, two academics working in this field, and seven people involved in the MERGE consortium. Participants were sent a discussion paper beforehand, which presented and recontextualised our research, described the interview process that preceded the event, the main insights gathered, and a first draft of recommendations.

During the roundtable, the MERGE consortium partners leading this task presented the key findings of the interviews and the set of recommendations. The event also benefited from input from two research projects that have addressed, or are addressing, similar research questions: the European Research Council (ERC) project CLIMGROW⁸ on the views of indicator producers on the design and influence of Beyond GDP metrics, and a PhD candidate exploring the perceived barriers and enablers in the implementation of wellbeing frameworks⁹.

After the presentations, breakout groups focused on discussing the following dimensions, which had emerged from the interviews:

- Enablers and constraints to developing and sustaining SIW frameworks at the national level
- Data and framework harmonisation
- Addressing the complexity of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing frameworks
- Data innovation

3. Key discussions and takeaways

The workshop was a key step in validating the insights gathered during the interviews and complementing them with new perspectives.

⁸ More information available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101097924>

⁹ No public results were available at the time of drafting this publication.

Enablers and constraints to developing SIW frameworks at the national level

A first part of the research focused on the enablers and constraints in developing and maintaining SIW frameworks at the national level. From the interviews, we had already identified the following enablers: political momentum and commitment, entrepreneurial NSI staff acting as internal champions, collaboration with civil society and researchers, funding, and international guidance. The roundtable participants validated those enablers and added the importance of having a conceptual framework around which to develop measurement. In terms of constraints, we had identified resource constraints¹⁰, competing political priorities, focus on statistics collected for existing reporting requirements (e.g. SDGs monitoring for the Voluntary Country Reviews), and perceived complexity of such frameworks. The roundtable validated those factors, highlighting resource constraints as the most important challenge, preventing data collection and limiting the possibilities for disaggregation. Additionally, from the discussion emerged three new constraints: persistent data gaps in some NSIs, notably in environmental data (compounded by a lack of resources for collecting this new data), a perceived lack of expertise in NSIs related to SIW framework, and a 'wait and see' attitude in some NSIs which perceive SIW research as an innovative field and would prefer to wait to see which innovations will prove robust before integrating them into formal frameworks.

Enablers and constraints to maintaining SIW frameworks at the national level

When it comes to maintaining a SIW framework over time, the interviewees stressed the importance of perceived political neutrality of the framework, NSI autonomy, existence of a legal framework mandating data reporting, relevance to policymaking, flexibility, transparency, and sound methodology. Roundtable participants validated those supportive factors. In the roundtable, the trustworthiness of NSI data in the eyes of the public was specifically highlighted as important. This was related to the idea that citizens should be able to see themselves in the data communicated. Indicators that do not resonate with lived experience can lead to distrust. Factors endangering framework maintenance were similar in the roundtable and the interviews: political change, new funding constraints, and limited use by policymakers.

Data and framework harmonisation

The second part of the workshop focused on the question of data harmonisation. We had

¹⁰ Developing new dashboards of indicators can be associated – among others - with costs related to data collection, human resources for developing and updating the framework, capacity-building of NSI staff, IT capacities, communication activities, public consultation activities.

already determined from the interviews a preference of NSIs for indicator harmonisation over framework harmonisation, or, as one interviewee put it, “*we should seek to standardise the coats, not the coat rack*”. This is linked to NSIs’ keenness to develop frameworks that are grounded in the national realities and priorities, possibly from citizen engagement and consultation. This was also the most common position among the roundtable participants. Still, participants recognised that, even though some level of national flexibility is desirable, having at least a harmonised set of headline indicators would be valuable for cross-country comparison¹¹. This was seen as particularly important for participants in favour of aggregating indicators into indices, so that comparisons of single numbers are possible. Harmonisation can also enhance the credibility of the data and the framework (as was seen with the international adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals [SDG] framework). For all these reasons, the work of the UN HLEG developing a clearly defined, globally accepted framework and its set of indicators was seen as valuable.

Addressing the complexity of SIW frameworks

Another key discussion point in the workshop was complexity. The workshop confirmed earlier findings that while large enough dashboards are important to ensure that the full multidimensionality of SIW is covered, and while governments should monitor a large range of indicators, these dashboards are hard to communicate or to understand when it comes to broader audiences. We identified five approaches for dealing with this complexity: identifying a small set of headline indicators, applying a traffic light system or other visualisation tools to make progress clearer, using adjusted economic indicators (such as adjusted-GDP measures), using indices, and minimising the number of domains. Participants voted to discuss the idea of headline indicators, which was considered in terms of strengths, challenges, and potential strategies to overcome those challenges. This solution was found to be a favourable option for easy communication to the public and policymakers, mitigating issues of cherry-picking in setting targets. However, participants expressed some concerns that the subset of headline indicators should be large enough to encapsulate SIW, that this could lead to reductionism in reducing SIW to a few priorities (that new governments would likely desire to change), and that framework harmonisation across countries would be more difficult. Various solutions were envisioned: further research on headline indicators, notably their ability to capture the statistical variation in a broader set

¹¹ The adoption by UN countries of the framework proposed by the UN High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP (published after this task’s final report) presents the strongest avenue for this. The HLEG calls upon government to “establish, by 2027, national progress-measuring initiatives using our proposed dashboard, tailored to country-specific needs and priorities”. A more detailed reflection on the final report from the HLEG and its recommendations can be found at the end of this section (c.f. Box 2).

and the ideal set size; complementing headline indicators with a larger set of secondary indicators; adopting the headline indicators internationally, creating indices.

Data innovation

Finally, the roundtable helped us expand our list of best practices and new data innovations. For example, one participant shared about the ONS work on developing the Open SDG, an open-source, free-to-use platform for managing and publishing data and statistics related to the SDGs.

4. Connection to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages

This research speaks of the institutional, political, and technical conditions of national statistical institutes, specifically with regard to SIW frameworks. In that sense, it can help contextualise the findings from the other technical deep dives of this WP5 by highlighting the broader political and institutional constraints within which NSIs' research operates. In addition, those findings directly inform the MERGE technical and policy guidelines and their online trainings (WP7 and WP8, respectively).

5. Operational guidelines for NSIs (next steps)

From the discussion in the roundtable and in the interviews, we extracted a set of recommendations that can provide avenues for NSIs aiming to develop, improve or maintain a national SIW framework. These recommendations replicate the ones made in the policy brief for NSI experts, a short document for communicating the main findings from the final report.

Develop a clear and coherent SIW framework

- **Clarify the framework's purpose.** Decide whether the framework aims to monitor overall societal progress or a specific policy area, and whether the primary audience is policy analysts, policymakers, or politicians and the public — or all three.
- **Adopt SIW as the conceptual basis.** A structure combining sustainability, inclusiveness, and wellbeing ensures coherence and compatibility with international developments. The public framing can be adapted to local realities.
- **Prioritise internationally harmonised indicators.** This supports comparability and prevents costly redesign later. Harmonisation covers survey question wording, mode, and response categories, not only domain coverage.

- **Include both subjective and objective indicators.** Subjective measures resonate with public and political audiences and improve trust in NSI data by aligning with citizens' lived experiences.
- **Engage citizens directly,** not only civil society. Citizens should ideally be engaged through deliberative panels or assemblies using sortition techniques to enhance democratic legitimacy and reduce the risk that the framework is perceived as the project of a particular government administration.

Establishing strong institutional foundations

- **Anchor the framework within the NSI,** as a transversal governmental body, rather than within a single ministry. A whole-of-governance approach, involving ministries, advisory councils, and data owners, builds shared ownership without dependency on any one actor.
- **Ensure perceived political neutrality.** Publish the criteria behind indicator selection, methodology, and metadata to maintain credibility across political cycles.
- **Build targeted internal capacity** in subjective wellbeing measurement, environmental statistics, geospatial analytics, administrative and big data, and science communication.
- **Establish data-sharing arrangements** with government departments and other data providers to improve access to administrative and third-party data.
- **Engage with international networks,** including the UN HLEG, the OECD Working Party on Wellbeing, relevant Commission (formal and informal) working groups, and Horizon Europe projects such as MERGE, for harmonisation support, capacity building, and cross-country learning.

Enhancing data availability and quality

- **Map existing datasets before pursuing new data collection.** Within the EU context, setting an SIW framework can often be done using existing datasets (e.g., regular statistical data, registers, EU-SILC, and administrative sources).
- **Use external funding strategically to fill critical conceptual gaps,** using Eurostat grants under the Single Market Programme and other EU programme funding where new data collection is genuinely necessary.
- **Leverage alternative and innovative data sources,** including register-based censuses with rolling surveys, augmented national accounts, geospatial data, and machine learning for nowcasting, where legally feasible.

Manage complexity and communicate effectively

- **Use a tiered indicator model.** Develop headline indicators as a top level, sitting above secondary indicators for policy work and a full dashboard for detailed analyses and researchers. Involve citizens in selecting headline indicators and consider legal devices to ensure durability through government change.
- **Use visual communication techniques** such as traffic-light systems, composite indices, or adjusted economic indicators to communicate the direction of change to politicians, journalists, and citizens.
- **Test communication with non-experts** to ensure resonance with citizens' lived experiences before publishing.

Strengthen policy use

- **Embed SIW in budget and policy processes** through budget tagging, ex-ante and ex-post assessments of budget impact, and mandatory wellbeing assessments — Italy's Budget Law and Ireland's budget tagging are working models.
- **Build regional and local applications.** Subnational dashboards are a particularly effective entry point where national political demand is weak, building policy allies at the regional and municipal levels.
- **Track and value intangible impacts**, including shifts in public narrative and political conversation, and document policy decisions where the framework can credibly claim to have played a role.

Box 2: Reflecting on the recommendations of UN High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP

A few months after the publication of this task's final deliverable and its attached policy briefs, the UN HLEG on Beyond GDP published its final report 'Counting What Counts: A Compass of Progress for People and Planet', on 7 May 2026 (High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP, 2026). This summary of the WP5 workshops is the opportunity to reflect on its recommendations.

The report that outlined the takeaways and recommendations of this task (See Abdallah et al (2025), Deliverable 5.1) called on NSIs to adopt SIW as a conceptual basis, ensuring comparability and coherence with international developments. Here, the HLEG's "conceptual framework for measuring equitable, inclusive and sustainable well-being and progress" constitutes a very promising step towards a global agreement on a common SIW framework – a key enabler for many NSIs looking to develop such an initiative at the national level.

The HLEG calls on the involvement of civil society organisations in establishing such frameworks. Based on the learnings of this task, we encourage involving citizens directly as well, when possible, to ensure an even stronger bottom-up approach and build ownership and awareness among the population.

The HLEG recommends increasing investments in data availability and statistical capacity, including through official development assistance and cooperation. This echoes our recommendations for engaging with international frameworks for harmonisation support, capacity building, and cross-country learning. Several EU Member States have already developed national SIW frameworks and can offer guidance and best practice examples to others.

Finally, the HLEG calls upon the international statistical community to develop emerging statistical methods to maturity, in particular for indicators relating to human rights, subjective wellbeing, planetary boundaries, social cohesion, and institutional capacity. This reflects our call for including subjective indicators, and the areas for innovation and harmonisation highlighted by interviewees and roundtable participants, which included social relations and loneliness and quantifying planetary boundaries overshoot (see page p45 of Deliverable 5.1).

ii. Workshop on comprehensive welfare measures

This workshop took place in the context of Task 5.1 Comprehensive welfare measures, led by Ghent University (UGent).

1. Background and concept

Ever since the development of the SNA, and its headline indicator Gross National Product (GNP) / Gross Domestic Product, aggregated monetary measures are central to economic policymaking. Ever since the early 1970s, economists have adjusted GNP (later GDP) to better reflect the welfare that economic activities generate. This “Beyond GDP” movement has led to a multitude of comprehensive welfare measures that use different methodologies. A lack of standardization within the Beyond GDP measurement space has often been cited as a main source of lack of political and policy uptake of such measures.¹²

The MERGE project's Task 5.1 workshop addressed limitations of GDP-based metrics, building on discussions since the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi report (2009) and contributed to the UN HLEG on measuring progress beyond GDP. The workshop focused on methodological developments that expand traditional boundaries of economic activities and capital stocks to more comprehensively measure welfare.

The workshop focused on two methodological developments in the Beyond GDP sphere: the Index of Sustainable Economic Welfare estimates for EU-27 (1995-2022) by UGent (building on Hicks-Fisher income concepts), and ONS's (United Kingdom Office for National Statistics) Inclusive Income Accounts (accounting-based welfare measurement where utility is based on consumption). These developments represent concrete examples supporting MERGE's transition from GDP to sustainable and inclusive wellbeing measurement. The measures typically start from GDP or consumption expenditures in the SNA and adjust these to take into account non-market activities (e.g., household labor, shadow economy), externalities (e.g., environmental degradation, road accidents) and depreciation of capital stocks beyond produced capital (e.g. natural capital stocks). Some of the measures also correct for the decreasing marginal utility of income and consumption to account for effect of income distribution on experienced welfare levels.

These comprehensive welfare measures directly support MERGE's first goal to harmonise data and gather cutting edge insights of measurement practice to empower statisticians

¹² Bleys, B., & Whitby, A. (2015). Barriers and opportunities for alternative measures of economic welfare. *Ecological Economics*, 117, 162–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2015.06.021>

with more rigorous tools to measure what really matters, while advancing the second goal to bring together diverse voices across and beyond academia to advance beyond GDP economics and create breakthroughs in knowledge and policy impact.

2. Workshop overview

MERGE consortium partners – UGent, ONS, the Joint Research Centre (JRC), Leiden University, University College of London and ARCO c/o PIN – together with the National Bank of Belgium jointly organized a two-day expert workshop in Brussels. The workshop was held on October 16-17, 2025 at the National Bank of Belgium.

The objective of the workshop was to bring together experts on (i) comprehensive welfare measures and (ii) the monetary valuation of non-market goods and services that enter such welfare measures, and this with the aim to exchange knowledge, improve methodologies and outline a research agenda for the field.

Participant profile

The workshop brought together 32 experts from major National Statistical Institutes (ONS; Istituto Nazionale di Statistica – ISTAT [Italy]; Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques – INSEE [France], National Bank of Belgium), international organizations (Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia, OECD, JRC, UN Statistical Division), and leading universities (Ghent University, University College London, Leiden University, University of Cambridge, King's College London, Stanford University, University of Sussex, University of Helsinki).

Programme structure

The workshop consisted of two main thematic sessions entitled: (i) Extending the boundaries of economic activity, and how to value this activity – including valuing household activities and volunteer work, and valuing ecosystem services; and (ii) Moving beyond exchange value totals – including accounting for externalities and incorporating distributional effects in monetary welfare measures. The final session of the workshop focused on co-creating a research agenda for the field, where participants jointly developed a list of research priorities for future methodological developments.

3. Key discussions and takeaways

Spectrum of economic welfare measures framework

A key conceptual contribution emerged through the joint work of ONS and UGent in developing a "Spectrum of Economic Welfare Measures" framework (see image below)

that connects the work that they have been carrying out independently up until the start of the MERGE project. This framework establishes a progression from narrowly defined measures of economic activity through to measures of utility, economic welfare, and well-being, providing a common language to talk about comprehensive welfare measures.

Concept	Market-Created Resources	Market, Government, and 3rd Sector Created Resources	All Economic Resource Creation	Sustainable Economic Resource Creation	Allocation of (Sustainable) Economic Resources	(Net) Utility		Well-being
Macroeconomic Headline Statistic(s)	Market GVA	GDP	Gross Inclusive Income, GDP-B	Net Inclusive Income	Adjusted Inclusive Income	ISEW Cost and Benefits Experienced Today	ISEW Costs and Benefits of Current Activities	Pluralistic dashboards of indicators
Additional Components		Public Services, FISIM, Production for Own Use*	Unpaid Household Work, Non-market ecosystem services	Capital Consumption, Natural Capital Depletion and Degradation	Externalities, Distributional accounts (-> Demographic growth rates)	Decreasing Marginal Utility of Income, Current Costs of Climate Change	Decreasing Marginal Utility of Income, Natural Capital Depletion, Externalities	Beyond Aggregation
Assumptions required for use as a welfare metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only market resources impact utility • Only current period consumption affects utility • Linear utility function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only market, gov, and 3rd sector resources impact utility • Only current period consumption affects utility • Linear utility function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All economic resources impact utility • Only current period consumption affects utility • Linear utility function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All economic resources impact utility • Linear utility function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All economic resources impact utility • Monotonic utility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All economic resources impact utility • Only current period consumption affects utility • Monotonic utility function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All economic resources impact utility • Monotonic utility 	
Micro-data	Turnover, pay, household income, etc.					Life-satisfaction, WELLBYs, willingness to pay		

The framework distinguishes measures ranging from Market-Created Resources (Market GVA) through All Economic Resource Creation (Gross Inclusive Income), Sustainable Economic Resource Creation (Net Inclusive Income), to Net Utility measures (ISEW). Each level requires additional assumptions about utility impacts, time horizons, and utility function specifications, helping understand how different comprehensive welfare measures relate to each other.

Extending the Boundaries of Economic Activity

Key insights emerged around expanding economic activity measurement through accounting-based methods, such as the Inclusive Wealth and Income Accounts, which expand national accounts logic to a wider variety of capital assets and economic activity, incorporating human capital, ecosystem services, unpaid household work, and natural capital depletion.

Workshop discussions highlighted that when trying to integrate market-equivalent value estimates back into national accounts, it becomes apparent that this results in

inconsistencies due to potential double-counting when existing markets already incorporate some non-market values. However, a key methodological advancement demonstrated that double entry accounting can be applied to externalities to resolve these inconsistencies.

Moving Beyond Exchange Value Totals

The second thematic focus addressed approaches incorporating externalities and distributional effects beyond market exchange values. Distributional accounting emerged as crucial for utilizing accounting rigor when estimating economic welfare, allowing for non-linear marginal utility of consumption. Workshop presentations showcased implementations including Distributional National Accounts and methodological advances in measuring household income growth distribution.

A fundamental question discussed related to how far the scope of goods and services should be widened in economic welfare measures, recognizing that in reality, there are numerous examples of non-market activities that will inevitably affect personal well-being but for which a price cannot be observed or even estimated.

Co-Created Research Agenda

During the final session, workshop participants jointly developed a list of research priorities for the field. The co-created research agenda identifies nine priority areas highlighted in the Table below.

Priority Areas for Comprehensive Measures of Welfare	
<i>1. Integrated Framework for Stocks, Flows, and Welfare</i>	
	Developing comprehensive frameworks integrating various capital forms (produced, natural, human, social) with income, consumption, services, and emissions flows, establishing clear production and asset boundaries to avoid inconsistencies.
<i>2. Distributional Aspects of Income, Consumption, and Wealth</i>	
	Analyzing distributional patterns among individuals and households, fundamental to addressing social equity within augmented accounts and developing distribution-sensitive welfare measures aligned with social welfare functions.
<i>3. Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions and Other Key Environmental Flows</i>	
	Incorporating emissions and environmental flows as integral welfare-relevant accounting components, advancing measurement and valuation methodologies (for example, using the Shadow Price of Carbon methodology) with connections to asset valuations and broader welfare measures.
<i>4. Integration of Ecosystem Services and Natural Capital</i>	
	Ensuring accurate measurement and valuation of ecosystem services within economic accounting systems as essential rather than peripheral components of national accounts.
<i>5. Capital Concepts and Measurement of Different Forms of Capital</i>	
	Defining and classifying capital types and their interrelationships within welfare-based frameworks, particularly examining whether social capital should be treated as distinct assets or intrinsic characteristics of other capital forms.

<i>6. Risk and Uncertainty in Augmented Accounts</i>	
	Incorporating risk factors including environmental uncertainties, socio-economic volatility, and potential disruptions into accounting frameworks for accurate real-world representation.
<i>7. Shadow Prices and Social Welfare Functions</i>	
	Developing methodologies for shadow prices and similar approaches aligned with social welfare functions, critical for valuing non-market goods and aggregating welfare while incorporating distributional concerns and risk factors.
<i>8. Communicating Concepts and Framework Usability</i>	
	Ensuring effective communication and usability of accounting frameworks, developing presentation methods for inclusive income measures and evaluating framing impacts on policy acceptance.
<i>9. Time Use and Household Production</i>	
	Examining unpaid work including caregiving, domestic labor, and volunteering, integrating time-use data into economic frameworks to understand gender inequalities and unpaid labor distribution.

These priorities represent consensus among leading experts on critical areas requiring continued research and development, providing a roadmap for advancing toward operational implementation in national statistical systems.

4. Connections to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages

Workshop discussions revealed clear connections to broader MERGE activities, particularly within WP5's technical deep dives (specifically time use surveys and wealth accounting). The topics discussed are relevant for statisticians and SNA practitioners working in NSIs, directly supporting MERGE technical and policy guidelines (WP7 and WP8) objectives of creating knowledge repositories and extracting recommendations for policymaking and advocacy purposes.

The workshop participants also jointly developed a reference list of academic works and grey literature on Beyond GDP topics related to comprehensive welfare measures for future WPs to build on.

5. Operational Guidelines for NSIs (next steps)

Assessment & Standardization

Workshop participants identified the need for comprehensive survey work to assess current NSI capabilities and development plans. It would be useful to survey NSIs on what parts of the Inclusive Income and Wealth Accounts they currently have in place, what parts they are planning to develop, and to inquire about plans to develop comprehensive welfare measures or other, augmented GDP type monetary measures. This assessment should be conducted

alongside NSIs evaluating their current capabilities against the spectrum of economic welfare measures framework developed during the workshop, identifying which components are already operational, which require development, and which comprehensive welfare measures could be feasibly implemented given existing data infrastructure.

Such overviews would help consolidate the state-of-the-art and provide a baseline for coordinated development efforts. The field would additionally benefit from internationally agreed upon standards on augmented national accounts and valuation methods to include additional costs and benefits from economic activities in welfare measures. The work within the UN (and especially the HLEG on Beyond GDP, and its proposal for well-being related national accounts) is deemed very relevant here for establishing methodological consistency across countries.

Implementation Pathways

Priority implementation areas include extending household satellite accounts, developing additional natural capital accounting components, and piloting distributional accounting approaches where data availability permits. The co-created research agenda provides specific methodological priorities that NSIs can pursue individually or through coordinated international efforts.

iii. Workshop on new methods in time use surveys

These two workshops were led by the ONS and were part of Task 5.2 New Methods in Time Use Surveys.

1. Background and concept

The ONS led on two workshops on new methods in time surveys, the first workshop focused on 'Online Data Collection Tools' and the second workshop focused on 'Using Frequent Online Time Use Data to Populate Household Satellite Accounts'. The aim of both the workshops together was to explore how to improve harmonisation in time use data collection, with a focus on collection tools and exploring further opportunities for collecting and utilising time use data. The first session showcased the UK's two online apps which support low-cost, regular time use survey collections. The session also highlighted the UK's plan to deliver a seven-year run of six-month interval Time Use Surveys to demonstrate the benefits of using online data collection tools and discussed best practices for implementing similar tools in other contexts. The second workshop focussed on using online time use data to populate faster and more timely Household Satellite accounts. The workshop discussed both data derived directly from the surveys and nowcasting to deliver a quarterly series of

Accounts data to highlight the benefits of using frequent online time use data and discuss best practices for utilizing this data to inform policymaking.

Time use surveys play a critical role in understanding how individuals and households allocate their most fundamental and equally shared resource: time. By documenting how the population distributes the fixed 24 hours of each day across activities such as paid work, unpaid care (such as caring of elders within households, community engagement, etc), leisure, and rest, time use data offers insights that go far beyond those captured in traditional labour market or household surveys. These data enable a more holistic understanding of daily life, social organisation, and the lived experience of different population groups. In doing so, time use surveys support analysis of quality of life, subjective well-being, health outcomes, environmental impacts, and social and gender inequalities, while also shedding light on economic production that falls outside conventional national accounts.

2. Workshop overview

MERGE consortium partners who were involved alongside ONS, were Leiden University, UGent, JRC, ZOE, PIN. The workshops were held online in January and February 2025.

Participant Profile

The workshops brought together a range of topic experts together from NSIs, academic and research community.

3. Key discussions and takeaways

Historically, time use data collection has relied heavily on pen-and-paper diary methods, particularly full diaries that allow respondents to describe activities in their own words. This approach has long been regarded as the gold standard due to its richness and flexibility. However, full diaries are costly and resource intensive for NSIs, place a significant burden on respondents, and require extensive post-collection processing. In response, some institutes have adopted “light diary” approaches, which limit reporting to a predefined list of activities (activities individuals are likely to engage in throughout the day) and typically focus on primary activities only. While these approaches reduce burden, they also reflect a trade-off between detail and feasibility.

At the same time, rapid technological change and increasing complexity in everyday life have intensified the need to modernise time use data collection. Although time itself remains fixed, the number, fragmentation, and simultaneity of daily activities have increased substantially. Digital technologies now offer practical alternatives to traditional diary

methods, making it possible to collect time use data more efficiently and more frequently, while also capturing additional dimensions such as location. In the UK, digital instruments such as the Office for National Statistics' Online Time Use Survey and the Centre for Time Use Research's ELiDDI demonstrate that online time use surveys can produce data of comparable quality to traditional Harmonised European Time Use Surveys, while delivering substantial cost and time efficiencies and maintaining broadly similar response rates.

Despite these advantages, digitalisation also introduces important challenges that require careful attention. The removal of face-to-face interviewers may reduce opportunities for clarification, probing, and respondent support, potentially increasing the risk of misinterpretation of survey questions. The relationship between interviewer presence, data quality, and response rates remains incompletely understood, and this issue extends beyond time use surveys to other national data collections that have transitioned to digital-only modes. Addressing these challenges requires systematic evaluation of digital methods, drawing on evidence from across household survey programmes.

Achieving meaningful and policy-relevant insights from time use data ultimately depends on a high degree of international harmonisation. NSIs play a central role in this process, particularly by adhering to common activity classifications, such as the HETUS framework, and maintaining consistency across survey waves and countries. However, harmonisation must extend beyond activity lists to encompass question wording, framing, and conceptual clarity. Certain activities such as supervisory care highlight the importance of this issue, as they may be experienced as enjoyable activities by some individuals and as burdensome obligations by others. Without careful design, surveys risk obscuring important differences in subjective well-being, emotional experience, and opportunity costs.

Looking ahead, time use data holds significant potential to inform public policy, particularly when linked to other data sources such as income, household composition, and health measures. It can illuminate how roles and responsibilities have evolved over time, how activity fragmentation and multitasking affect well-being, and how time pressures differ across gender, income groups, and household types. Realising this potential requires continued methodological innovation, rigorous testing and piloting, and a coordinated international approach that balances efficiency with conceptual depth and data quality.

The Household Satellite Accounts workshop brought together a diverse set of international perspectives to address a shared challenge: how to better measure, value, and integrate unpaid household work into economic frameworks that have traditionally focused on market-based activity. Across country experiences and research initiatives, a common

message emerged, unpaid work is foundational to economic functioning and social well-being yet remains largely invisible in headline economic statistics and policy debates.

A central theme of the discussions was the scale and significance of unpaid household services, including childcare, adult care, cooking, cleaning, transport, and volunteering. Evidence from UK demonstrates that when valued systematically, unpaid household production represents a substantial share of economic activity, often equivalent to a quarter or more of GDP, and in some cases exceeding half of conventional GDP measures.¹³ These findings challenge prevailing narratives about economic growth and productivity, highlighting that a large proportion of value creation occurs outside the market economy. Participants emphasised that ignoring this domain risks underestimating living standards, misrepresenting distributional outcomes, and overlooking the true drivers of individual and societal wellbeing.

Methodologically, the workshop highlighted both convergence and innovation. Most countries currently rely on input-based approaches that combine time use data with replacement wage rates, reflecting pragmatic responses to data availability constraints. However, several initiatives are expanding beyond this baseline, experimenting with output-based methods, hybrid valuations, and integration with labour accounts. Across all approaches, high-quality time use data was consistently identified as the critical underpinning. While time use surveys are indispensable, their infrequent collection, evolving design, and limitations in capturing multitasking, care, and seasonal activities remain key constraints. As a result, many teams are investing in improved survey instruments, digital collection modes, nowcasting techniques, and open-source analytical pipelines to enhance timeliness, transparency, and reproducibility.

Gender inequality and demographic differentials featured prominently throughout the discussions. Across all country cases, women continue to perform substantially more unpaid work than men, often two to three times as much, with the largest burdens concentrated among parents and those in mid-life who balance paid work with caring responsibilities. The “sandwich generation” (a generation of middle-aged people usually responsible for bringing up their own children and caring for elderly members of the household) and single-parent households were repeatedly identified as groups facing particularly intense time pressures.

¹³ See for instance Household Satellite Account, UK - Office for National Statistics (<https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/nationalaccounts/satelliteaccounts/bulletins/householdsatelliteaccountuk/2023>) and Inclusive wealth and income accounts, UK - Office for National Statistics (<https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/economicoutputandproductivity/output/articles/ukinclusiveincome/2005to2023>).

Importantly, participants stressed that unpaid work not only reflects existing inequalities but also actively shapes them, influencing labour market participation, income trajectories, and long-term welfare outcomes. Evidence from the United States, for example, shows that declines in unpaid household production have disproportionately affected lower-income households, weakening the equalising role that unpaid work once played and amplifying overall inequality. Put simply, lower-income households used to rely more on unpaid household production such as cooking, childcare, and home maintenance which acted as a form of “hidden income” and helped reduce differences in living standards. When this unpaid work is taken into account, inequality in overall resources (or “true income”) was smaller than what is shown by measured income alone.

Over time, however, unpaid household production in the United States has declined more for these lower-income households, and this loss has not been matched by an equivalent increase in paid income. As a result, the ability of unpaid work to reduce inequality has weakened, contributing to a wider gap in overall living standards. Several contributions extended the discussion beyond valuation toward broader questions of well-being, sustainability, and societal choice. The WISE Horizon project¹⁴ illustrated how time use data can be combined with environmental and well-being indicators to explore low-carbon, high-well-being futures. This work demonstrated that activities associated with high enjoyment are often low in carbon intensity, while some high-carbon activities deliver relatively low well-being returns. Scenario analysis further underscored that increases in unpaid care without accompanying systemic support can reduce enjoyment and exacerbate inequalities, particularly for women. These insights reinforced the idea that time use is not only an analytical tool, but also a powerful way to communicate complex policy trade-offs to policymakers and the public.

The workshop also underscored the growing policy relevance of household satellite accounts. Integrating unpaid work into national accounts, labour statistics, and distributional analyses enables a more complete understanding of economic transitions, including shifts driven by demographic change, female labour force participation, and care needs associated with ageing populations. Participants noted that welfare and labour market policies often implicitly assume unpaid work to be costless or infinitely elastic, an assumption that becomes increasingly flawed as household production capacity declines. Making unpaid work visible helps to reveal hidden trade-offs, assess the true impacts of policy reforms, and design support systems that better reflect how societies function in practice.

¹⁴ More information available at: <https://wisehorizons.world/>

At the same time, participants were clear about the challenges that lie ahead. International standardisation remains a work in progress, with ongoing efforts by international organisations to refine definitions, classifications, and conceptual boundaries. Cultural context, data availability, and policy priorities mean that countries are progressing at different speeds and with different emphases. Rather than waiting for perfect global standards, many contributors advocated for scalable, defensible approaches that can evolve over time while remaining transparent about assumptions and limitations.

In concluding discussions, the workshop returned to a broader reflection on how economies are conceptualised and measured. When unpaid household work is fully taken into account, the distinction between market and non-market economies becomes blurred, raising fundamental questions about the adequacy of GDP as a standalone measure of progress. Participants emphasised that assigning a monetary value to unpaid work is not an end in itself, but a means of enriching economic narratives, informing better policy decisions, and supporting a shift toward more inclusive, well-being-focused frameworks. Ultimately, the workshop highlighted that advancing this agenda depends on sustained investment in data, continued methodological innovation, and close collaboration between statisticians, researchers, and policymakers.

4. Connection to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages

The outputs of this task were condensed into a summary document (see Annex) which serves as a basis for technical guidance material in WP7. The summaries aim to provide a clear and concise overview of the benefits of using online data collection tools and frequent time use data, as well as best practices to inform policymaking.

5. Operational guidelines for NSIs (next steps)

- **Make time use data a core statistical input:** NSIs should move toward regular, consistent time use data collection, using digital methods where appropriate while actively monitoring impacts on data quality and response behaviour. Robust time use data underpins both well-being analysis and household satellite accounts.
- **Improve clarity in measuring unpaid work:** Greater attention is needed in survey design to ensure unpaid activities particularly care and supervisory responsibilities are clearly defined and consistently interpreted. Piloting alternative question wording and classifications can significantly improve analytical value.

- **Integrate unpaid work into mainstream economic statistics:** Household satellite accounts should be more closely linked with labour accounts, income statistics, and distributional frameworks, rather than treated as stand-alone outputs. This supports more complete “beyond GDP” narratives.
- **Strengthen inequality and gender analysis:** NSIs should systematically use time use and unpaid work data to examine gender, household, and income inequalities, making transparent how unpaid work shapes extended income, time poverty, and well-being.
- **Improve timeliness and transparency:** Investing in faster production pipelines, open-source tools, and clear documentation of assumptions will improve policy relevance and trust, even where methods continue to evolve.
- **Engage in harmonisation while remaining pragmatic:** NSIs should actively contribute to international standards while adopting scalable national approaches that can evolve over time, rather than waiting for full global consensus.
- **Focus on policy relevance, not just valuation:** Unpaid work estimates should be framed as tools to understand trade-offs in care, labour markets, sustainability, and well-being not simply as monetary totals.

iv. Workshops on wealth accounting

These two workshops led by the UK ONS took place in the context of Task 5.4 Wealth Accounting

1. Background and concept

The ONS led on two workshops as part of task 5.4. The first workshop focused on what counts as ‘capital’? This workshop provoked discussions around the flexible boundary of what is in scope and how we should conceptualize social capital, heritage capital, cultural capital, organizational capital. The workshop helped to identify the key issues surrounding capital accounting and generate ideas for improving the current framework. The second workshop was on how much do different methods to estimate the value of capital matter? This workshop provoked a discussion around the different methods to consider both current price estimation of different capitals; their differences and similarities, and the impact of different methods of estimating price deflators, with a focus on accounting prices, which strive to capture externalities. The workshop aimed to identify the key issues surrounding the valuation of capital and generate ideas for improving the current framework.

2. Workshop overview

MERGE consortium partners who were involved alongside ONS were: Leiden University, UGent, JRC, ZOE, PIN. The workshops were held online in October and November 2025.

Participant Profile

The workshops brought together a range of topic experts together from NSIs, academic and research community.

3. Key discussions and takeaways

The two wealth accounting workshops collectively advanced a shared ambition to develop more comprehensive and policy-relevant measures of national wealth that move beyond GDP and better reflect long-term sustainability, well-being, and resilience. Across both events, participants explored how established national accounting frameworks can be expanded to incorporate a broader range of capital assets, while retaining conceptual clarity, internal consistency, and international comparability.

A central theme was the role of the SNA as the anchor for inclusive wealth accounting. Both workshops stressed that extending measurement boundaries must build on, rather than bypass, national accounting principles. This approach enables different forms of capital to be assessed within a coherent structure that links stocks and flows, investment and depreciation, and current prosperity with future well-being. Inclusive wealth was consistently framed as complementary to GDP: not a replacement, but a framework that reveals whether economic activity is building or eroding the foundations of future welfare.

Significant discussion focused on expanding production and asset boundaries to reflect economic realities that are insufficiently captured in traditional accounts. This included unpaid household production, ecosystem services, human capital, cultural heritage, and a growing range of intangible and digital assets. Participants recognised that many of these assets generate real economic and social value but lack clear market prices, identifiable ownership, or exclusive benefits. As a result, they are systematically undervalued or omitted entirely from conventional balance sheets.

The workshops also highlighted conceptual challenges around valuation, ownership, and sustainability. Social capital, cultural capital, and global environmental systems such as the atmosphere were used to illustrate the limits of treating all value as privately owned assets. Different conceptual treatments were discussed, including viewing some capitals as enabling factors that support other assets, or in the case of global ecosystems treating

degradation as a national liability rather than an owned asset. These discussions were closely linked to debates on strong versus weak sustainability and the extent to which losses in natural capital can be offset by gains in other forms of capital.

Methodologically, the workshops reinforced the need for plural and pragmatic valuation approaches. Three broad traditions cost-based, perpetual inventory, and income-based methods were discussed, each with strengths and limitations depending on the type of asset. A key insight was that non-standardisation and non-exclusivity, rather than intangibility alone, pose the greatest measurement challenges. For many assets, particularly natural, cultural, and social capital, income-based approaches using discounted future benefits are often the most defensible, despite their reliance on assumptions.

Across both workshops, shadow pricing emerged as essential for capturing social and environmental values not reflected in markets, particularly for climate impacts, ecosystem services, health benefits, and cultural value. Participants consistently endorsed an “improvement over perfection” principle: focusing first on major externalities and high-impact areas rather than waiting for comprehensive but impractical solutions. Triangulating multiple valuation approaches for the same asset was also encouraged as a way to improve understanding and transparency.

A further unifying theme was policy relevance. Wealth accounting was repeatedly framed as a practical tool for informing long-term decision-making, rather than a purely academic exercise. Integrated wealth and productivity measures were shown to have clear applications in climate policy, infrastructure investment, health and education spending, heritage preservation, and regional development. Participants emphasised that clarity of communication using plain language and coherent narratives is as important as technical sophistication if these accounts are to influence policy.

Taken together, the workshops underscored that wealth accounting is at a pivotal stage of development. While conceptual and empirical challenges remain, there is broad agreement on both direction and principles to extend national accounts to better reflect modern sources of value; be transparent about assumptions and limitations; prioritise integration and comparability; and focus on measures that illuminate sustainability and future well-being. Incremental progress along these lines can significantly strengthen the role of official statistics in shaping more informed and forward-looking economic policy.

4. Connection to other MERGE technical deep dives and work packages

The outputs of this task were condensed into a summary document (see Annex) serves as a basis for guidance material in WP6 and WP7. The summaries are designed to identify proposed strategies for moving forward within the beyond GDP landscape that aims to develop a future-facing strategy for capital measurement.

5. Operational guidelines for NSIs (next steps)

The wealth accounting workshops point to a shared direction of travel for National Statistical Institutes, moving from experimental extensions of national accounts toward more operational, policy-relevant systems for measuring inclusive wealth. Achieving this requires both conceptual discipline and pragmatic implementation grounded in national accounting principles.

First, NSIs should continue to anchor inclusive wealth measures firmly in the SNA. Using national accounting as the organising framework ensures conceptual coherence, avoids double counting, and allows new forms of capital to be integrated in ways that are comparable over time and across countries. Inclusive wealth should complement GDP by linking capital stocks to flows of income, depreciation, revaluations, and genuine savings, thereby revealing whether current economic activity is building or eroding the foundations of future well-being.

Second, asset boundaries need to be expanded in a controlled and transparent manner. This includes systematically incorporating human capital, natural capital, household production assets, cultural heritage, and key intangible assets. NSIs must clearly articulate scope decisions, explain what is included and excluded, and document how overlaps between capitals are handled, particularly where values are non-market or shared across society.

The workshops also highlight the need for stronger conceptual clarity for ‘difficult’ capitals, such as social capital, cultural capital, and global environmental systems. NSIs should explicitly test and present alternative treatments whether as distinct assets, enabling capitals that support others, or liabilities reflecting degradation (as in the case of climate damage). Making these assumptions explicit is essential for analytical credibility and policy interpretation.

Methodologically, NSIs should prioritise the development and application of shadow pricing, focusing first on major externalities with clear policy relevance, such as climate change, ecosystem services, and health and well-being impacts. An “improvement over perfection”

principle should guide this work, recognising that capturing the largest distortions in market prices delivers the greatest analytical returns.

Given the diversity of capital types, the workshops strongly supported methodological pluralism. NSIs should avoid relying on a single valuation approach and instead triangulate across cost-based, reproduction, and income-based methods where feasible. This is particularly important for non-market, non-exclusive, and non-standardised assets, where uncertainty is unavoidable and needs to be clearly communicated.

To increase policy impact, wealth accounting must also become timelier and more operational. NSIs should invest in repeatable production pipelines, improved data integration, and clearer links between wealth accounts and policy-relevant indicators. This shifts wealth accounting from occasional analytical outputs toward a regular input into long-term economic and sustainability assessments.

Finally, progress toward international harmonisation should continue alongside national innovation. While engagement with emerging standards is essential, NSIs should not delay implementation while waiting for full consensus. Scalable national approaches, transparently documented, can evolve as international frameworks mature. Clear communication using accessible language and policy-focused narratives is crucial to ensure wealth accounting informs real-world decision-making.

III. Final reflections and next steps

All in all, these six co-creative workshops carried out in the MERGE project as technical and data deep dives enabled us to explore the opportunities and pathways that can be undertaken towards improving measurement efforts in the area of SIW and underscored the importance of implementing these new metrics. The proliferation of concrete approaches like time use, wealth accounting, and comprehensive welfare measurement represent a broader shift in the socio-political understanding of progress, moving beyond narrow economic metrics towards measurement frameworks that recognise the distribution of resources, the value of unpaid contributions, the sustainability of wealth, and the multidimensional nature of societal wellbeing. Ultimately, their relevance lies not only in improving statistics, but in reshaping the evidence base that informs public priorities, governance choices, and long-term societal resilience.

Through these exercises, described in detail in the previous section, we have identified a series of specific takeaways and concrete recommendations directed specifically to NSIs on how to move forward. At the same time, the workshops highlighted several practical areas

where progress is already possible, including the greater use of harmonised headline indicators, the integration of time use data and unpaid work into official statistics, the expansion of wealth accounting frameworks, and the adoption of innovative data collection methods capable of improving both timeliness and policy relevance.

In addition to these, it is also possible to identify some cross-cutting insights that emerged as a common thread. A first group of reflections focused on the interactions needed to set in motion the technical reforms and statistical innovations necessary for developing SIW measurement frameworks. Here, partnership between NSIs and academic researchers was highlighted as an important collaboration for exploring cutting-edge ideas and fostering creativity in each thematic domain. While in the European setting these interactions have become more frequent, there is still room to embed them more structurally, using this as an opportunity to ensure their inclusiveness and timeliness. Similarly, engagement with “frontrunners” NSIs working at the frontier of the topic can be a fruitful way forward, especially for NSIs that are smaller in size and have limited capacity to push for innovations that have not been piloted elsewhere. Lastly, political will and momentum, including coming from international spaces, were recognised as the essential driver for pushing forward novel frameworks at early stages, as well as for their effective adoption and long-term institutionalisation. In this scenario, the UN HLEG recommendations and the upcoming intergovernmental process are particularly promising. The workshops also showed that innovation often depends on the availability of internal expertise and dedicated resources. Several participants pointed to persistent capability gaps in areas such as environmental statistics, subjective wellbeing measurement, geospatial analysis, and the use of alternative data sources, suggesting that capacity-building efforts will be as important as methodological development.

A second cluster of common reflections was about how to move from ideas to solutions that can be plausibly implemented by NSIs. In this sense, it is worth highlighting that the SNA plays a crucial role in shaping the work of NSIs; thus, when proposals are directly connected to the SNA, they become easier to operationalise. As a practical recommendation, having the SNA more regularly updated would create a fertile ground to create the space for further innovations. However, it was also noted that feasibility, while important, should not limit ambition and creativity, and that space for critical exploration of better alternatives is also crucial. This is particularly noticeable in the area of distributional effects. The tension between feasibility and ambition was especially visible in discussions on comprehensive welfare measures, household production, and wealth accounting, where participants repeatedly emphasised the importance of extending accounting boundaries while

preserving conceptual consistency and avoiding double counting. Similarly, the time use survey workshops demonstrated that digital collection tools and nowcasting methods offer realistic pathways to improve the frequency and policy relevance of data, even where resource constraints make traditional survey approaches increasingly difficult to sustain.

Lastly, the need for harmonisation also emerged as a common thread: While innovation and creative solutions are developed continuously, efforts are frequently scattered and need to be aligned. Once again, international guidance can help pave the way forward, offering solutions that can be adopted and replicated at the national level. International collaboration yields multiple potential benefits that range from socialising best practices to minimising costs. While the UN HLEG on Beyond GDP was noted as an important process that could offer valuable guidance across the different topics covered, in the European context, there is also a potential role for technical agencies – like Eurostat, JCR and OECD – to contribute to this endeavour. Across the workshops, harmonisation was generally viewed as more valuable at the level of indicators, classifications, and methodological standards than at the level of complete frameworks. Nonetheless, it was also noted that this should not inhibit national innovation and that NSIs should remain pragmatic in their approach. In fact, participants favoured retaining flexibility to reflect national priorities while pursuing greater convergence in core indicators, survey instruments, valuation methods, and accounting practices. In particular, common approaches to time use statistics, household satellite accounts, natural capital accounting, and distributional measures were identified as promising areas for future coordination.

As a final reflection, this last topic offers the opportunity to widen the debate and discuss more generally the enabling conditions that would support and foster innovation in the field of SIW in NSIs, along with the role of other stakeholders (in particular policymakers) and institutions in doing so. In addition to guidance, harmonisation (and innovation) also requires proper resourcing, including sufficient funding and appropriate capabilities. At the moment, these issues remain among the most important challenges that NSIs face when it comes to developing and implementing innovative and socially relevant indicators in the area of SIW; a challenge that cannot be solved completely in the technical realm, as it requires policy direction and support. Hence, policymakers can be instrumental in creating the enabling conditions for the emergence of robust, reliable, and creative SIW measuring frameworks. Moreover, in this scenario, it would become crucial to provide more stability in terms of policy priorities and support continuity, ensuring that as administrations change, existing mechanisms are not dismantled, and accumulated knowledge is not lost. Likewise, policymakers play a crucial role in formally adopting and mainstreaming the use of these

tools, embedding them in the policy cycle (from design to evaluation) and ensuring they remain politically relevant and are effectively implemented. Without such long-term commitment, early encouragement for piloting and experimentation risks backfiring, as developers cannot demonstrate the value of the tools they create if there is no political will to use them. On these matters, the forthcoming MERGE technical and policy guidelines (to be released in September 2026) will offer guidance on how to embrace SIW in measurement frameworks and policy processes, with a particular focus on the European setting. Together, their ambition is to contribute to really make SIW the overarching policy goal to guide governance and policy choices in accordance with European values and for the benefit of its long-term prosperity and resilience.

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Annex

Additional materials (summaries, background papers, agendas) can be found at:

<https://mergeproject.eu/event-materials/>

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